

Developing a High Level Preservation Strategy for Virtual Reality Artworks

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No Time To Wait 3, BFI, London
23 October 2018

Supported by Carla Rapoport, Lumen Art Projects Ltd.

Introduction

- Moving from exploratory research to strategy for acquisition and preservation
- First stages of project have explored:
 - The core components of VR systems (software and hardware) and their relationships
 - Production and playback of 360 video VR works
 - Production and playback of real-time 3D VR works
 - Initial exploration of preservation strategies for both the above

VR System Overview: Hardware

VR System Overview: Software

VR Platform Fragmentation

Image credit: Khronos Group
<https://www.khronos.org/openxr/>

360 Video: Production

Capture: Monoscopic 360 with dual fisheye lenses

Image credit: <http://theta360.guide/plugin-guide/fisheye/>

360 Video: Production

Capture: Stereoscopic 360 with multiple lenses

Image credit: <https://www.mysterybox.us/blog/2017/1/31/shooting-360-vr-with-gopro-odyssey-and-google-jump-vr>

360 Video: Production

Capture: Stereoscopic 360 with multiple lenses

360 Video: Production

Common file characteristics

Containers	MP4, MKV
Aspect Ratio	Equirectangular 2:1
Frame rates	Commonly 60 fps
Resolution	4096 x 2048- equivalent to 1024 FOV
Compression	H264, H265

360 Video: Playback

Equirectangular

360 Video: Playback

Cubemap

360 Video: **Playback**

Pyramid

Image credit: <https://code.fb.com/virtual-reality/next-generation-video-encoding-techniques-for-360-video-and-vr/>

360 Video: Playback

Top bottom stereoscopic 360 equirectangular projection

Identifying string: “3dv” or “_tb”

examplemedia_3dv_.mp4

Left right stereoscopic 360 equirectangular projection

Identifying string: “3dh” or “_lr”

examplemedia_3dh_.mp4

360 Audio: **Production**

“A” Format
Raw audio

“B” Format
Amplitude and spatial information

360 Audio: **Production**

Audio encoding	WAV, AIFF, AAC
Ambisonic “order” or number of channels	4, 9, 16
Audio channel ordering	Furse-Malham, ACN
Audio channel spherical normalisation	SN3D, maxN, N3D.

360 Audio: **Playback**

- Direct sound
- Filtered sound through head delayed
- Diffracted sound around head delayed

Real-Time 3D: **Production**

- **Assets** created using various proprietary and open-source tools and brought together in an engine
- Assets typically portable with open file format potential in some cases:
 - **3D models:** meshes and materials
 - **Textures:** texture maps (raster images)
 - **Sounds:** Ogg Vorbis and WAV
- **glTF** as open standard for archiving?

glTF succeeds Collada as
an open spec file format
for 3D asset/scene

3D Modelling: Meshes and UVs

Mesh

+

UV Map

3D Modelling: Materials and Textures

Real-Time 3D: Production

- **Engines** typically non-portable and proprietary/licenced
- Engines integrate assets and engine features in scenes/levels and include:
 - Lighting
 - Material shaders
 - Physics
 - Visual or typed scripting
 - Sound engine
 - Plugins and extensions

Real-Time 3D: **Playback**

- Built as executable software package
- Usually consists of executable file(s) and packaged assets
- Can be executed in a specific technical environment which might include:
 - **VR Runtimes** e.g. SteamVR, Oculus Runtime, OpenXR, WebVR etc.
 - **Graphics API** e.g. DirectX, Metal, OpenGL, Vulkan etc.
 - **Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) and driver**

Vulkan is an open standard for cross-platform 3D graphics which succeeds OpenGL

Rendering Pipeline

VR Rendering Pipeline

Lens Distortion

- Lenses used in headset to achieve wide field of view at close range
- Distortion must be corrected for in the frames send to headset
- Usually carried out as post processing
- Process specified by VR runtime

Image credit: Christian Pötzsch <https://www.imgtec.com/blog/speeding-up-gpu-barrel-distortion-correction-in-mobile-vr/>

Timewarp & Spacewarp

- Predictive interpolation of frames
- Distorts previously generated frame based on movement of user and scene
- Low cost tricks to maintain high framerate and low latency
- Process specified by VR runtime

Image credit: Neo222

https://xinreality.com/wiki/Asynchronous_Spacewarp

An Open Standard for VR Runtimes?

- The Khronos Group is a consortium of industry partners who develop open standards for 3D graphics
- **OpenXR** is working group attempting to develop a VR runtime standard
- All the big players in the VR industry are involved
- Like glTF and Vulkan, could also benefit preservation efforts... if it is adopted

Image credit: Khronos Group <https://www.khronos.org/openxr/>

Next Steps: Exploring Preservation Strategies

	General	360 Video	Real-Time 3D
Migration	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Headset lens distortion algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Moving between projection types• Variability in players	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• How reliable are the open 3D asset standards• Re-creating a 3D scene in different engines
Emulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emulating VR runtimes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emulating 360 video players	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Paravirtualization and passthrough for real-time 3D VR
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Field of view video capture• Accounts of experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Documenting projection type	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 360 video capture

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